

Towards Efficient Consistency Management for Informal Applications

Jan Scheffczyk

Uwe M. Borghoff

Peter Rödiger

Lothar Schmitz⁰

Universität der Bundeswehr, München

Abstract

When a group of authors collaboratively edits interrelated documents, consistency problems occur almost immediately. Current document management systems (DMS) often lack adequate facilities for consistency management. We extend traditional DMS by explicit formal consistency rules. In contrast to many other approaches, we *permit inconsistencies* and present the consequences to the user, which is vital for flexible document management and information management. Based on a novel semantics our tools pinpoint inconsistencies precisely.

In this paper we focus on a key issue: efficient techniques for consistency rule evaluation. Our strategy is known from databases: (1) static analysis characterizes and simplifies consistency rules, (2) at run-time rules are evaluated incrementally. The major differences to databases are that we consider informal documents and explicitly allow inconsistencies. Consequently, we do not have formal update descriptions and cannot rely on consistency prior to updates. This makes incremental consistency checking a real challenge.

The contribution of this paper is to incrementally evaluate consistency rules in the presence of previous inconsistencies. We have implemented our techniques in a revision control system. Our experiments show that efficient incremental evaluation provides the key to making our approach viable.

Keywords: information management, document management, consistency, incremental evaluation.

1. Introduction

Usually, a multitude of authors is involved in producing larger bodies of writing that contain many interrelated documents,¹ such as books, technical documentations, software specifications, or even internet sites. Mainstream document management systems (DMS) store documents in a repository and administer document versions and author's access rights. Such DMS lack, however, adequate facilities to manage semantic consistency requirements between documents. Thus

authors are forced to spend much time re-reading and revising their own and related documents in order to achieve semantic consistency. Worse, each check-in to the repository can violate consistency again. Larger companies define guidelines and policies for writing; but still a *human* reviewer is needed to enforce them. What prevents automatic consistency checks is that guidelines are implicit or at best informal.

This motivates the use of formal consistency rules to capture semantic constraints between documents. For flexible document management it is vital to allow inconsistencies w.r.t. these rules [10, 20]. Thus the central question is about *how* inconsistent a repository is, and not whether inconsistencies occur at all. In [28] we have employed typed first-order temporal predicate logic with linear time and have extended boolean semantics in order to generate consistency reports. These reports precisely point out inconsistent document parts.

Speed is a key to user acceptance. After a check-in to the repository, authors want to know almost immediately whether this check-in is accepted and how it meets the consistency rules. In this paper we address the issue of *efficiently* evaluating first-order linear temporal consistency rules against a heterogeneous repository. In contrast to many other approaches we retain our tolerant semantics. We improve efficiency by two measures: First, we reduce checking complexity by static analysis, which is performed prior to evaluating consistency rules. Second, we reduce the complexity of the evaluation algorithm itself during evaluation. Static rule analysis attempts to decrease the number of rules to be re-evaluated at a check-in by filtering and to decrease the static computational complexity of a rule by rewriting. Our evaluation algorithm dynamically reduces quantifier domains. Since we permit inconsistencies we employ an incremental algorithm that makes heavy use of previous consistency reports.

This paper is organized as follows: In Sect. 2 and Sect. 3 we summarize our extensions to a typical DMS, the abstract syntax of consistency rules, and our tolerant semantics. Sect. 4 forms the heart of this paper by detailing our techniques to speed up the evaluation of consistency rules. We outline our implementation and present some lessons learned from practical experiments in Sect. 5. Related work is discussed in Sect. 6. In Sect. 7 we draw final conclusions and show directions for future research.

Throughout this paper, we use the following example. In practice we find far more complex examples that raise closely related problems [16, 33, 32]. Although our example may appear too simple at first sight, we use it for *illustration*. For a more complex scenario see our case study [30].

⁰Institute for Software Technology
Werner-Heisenberg-Weg 39, 85577 Neubiberg, Germany
{jan.borghoff,roedig,lothar}@informatik.unibw-muenchen.de
This work has been sponsored by the Universität der Bundeswehr München.

¹Documents do not need to follow a common formal document model, such as XML.

Figure 1. Example repository

Example 1 Assume that we want to archive manuals over a long period of time. Documents (and manuals) reference manuals through a key (see Fig. 1). Since names and kinds of manuals may change over time we need key resolvers mapping keys to their semantics, i.e., manual kind and name. Multiple key resolvers may exist. Their actual names are hidden from authors. In order to ensure consistency we require that (1) (two-step) links to manuals are valid and (2) names and kinds of manuals are invariant over time. A reference to a key k is valid if k is defined in a key resolver and this definition points to an existing manual of the correct kind.

Let a toy repository contain a plain text document doc1.txt and two XML documents: a key resolver keys.xml and a manual man1.xml. The second check-in causes two inconsistencies: (1) the key reference to kaA3 is inconsistent because the kind of man1.xml is different from the kind of the key definition for kaA3; (2) the kind of man1.xml has changed. □

2. Consistency-Aware Document Management Systems

Formalizing consistency rules causes complexity in various problem areas. Therefore, we divide formalization into different tasks and supply tools to every stakeholder (see Fig. 2).

From a repository, authors typically check out document working copies, modify them, and finally check them in again. Among other things, a classic DMS manages concurrent check-ins, author's permissions, version control, and repository backup. We design our consistency checker in a way that makes only few assumptions about the DMS. We require (1) access to the versions of a document that have been checked in, (2) a locking mechanism that prevents check-ins during a consistency check, and (3) information about which documents have been modified by an update. In particular, we make no assumptions about the document model of the DMS, such that our extensions also apply to revision control systems like CVS [7].

A rule designer formalizes consistency rules – they reflect wishes from the “administrator” perspective. We distinguish between strict rules, which must be adhered to, and weak rules, which may be violated. The repository is checked for consistency at given events, e.g., document check-in. For each rule this generates a consistency report, to which we can

Figure 2. System overview (ovals mark fixed components; rectangles mark customizable components)

react in various ways. Upon violation of a weak rule, the system could inform those authors who have checked out (now) inconsistent documents. If, however, a strict rule is violated the system will reject the check-in in question. In addition, the rule designer creates templates for documents. These will be DTDs or Schemas if XML is used. Consistency rules use function symbols and predicate symbols from domain specific languages. A static type system ensures well-typedness of rules w.r.t. the languages used. We provide a basic language, which defines some fundamental function and predicate symbols, as for example =, denoting equality.

In user-defined languages a language designer declares domain specific function symbols, predicate symbols, and types. Symbol semantics is defined in Haskell [23] – a statically typed purely functional programming language. As described in Sect. 4, Haskell’s referential transparency provides fundamental support for our incremental evaluation algorithm. Also, Haskell gives access to other libraries via a foreign function interface [8]. Such libraries offer sophisticated functionality, e.g., for parsing documents or heuristics for semantic content analysis [4, 27]. Formal document types (usually corresponding to document templates) can be expressed by record or variant types. This makes our approach independent of a particular document format and facilitates heterogeneous repositories. For our running example, a record type ResD defines the formal structure of key resolvers. If XML is used, document types and parser function implementations can be derived from XML DTDs [35]. Note that complex programming tasks are hidden from the rule designer who needs simple first-order logic only.

For specific projects, a project manager chooses consis-

$\phi, \psi ::= p(e_1, \dots, e_n)$	atomic formula
$\neg\phi$ $\phi \wedge \psi$	negation, conjunction
$\phi \vee \psi$ $\phi \Rightarrow \psi$	disjunction, implication
$\forall x \in e \bullet \phi$	universally quantified formula
$\exists x \in e \bullet \phi$	existentially quantified formula
$e ::= x$	variable
f	function symbol or record label
$f(e_1, \dots, e_n)$	application

Figure 3. Formal consistency rule syntax

tency rules. In some cases adaptations will be necessary, e.g., some rules can be weakened. Of course, major changes to the document templates cause adaptations to the corresponding formal document types, which may involve further changes in the language. But in our experience most projects require layout related adaptations only.

3. Consistency Rules

In this section we introduce the syntactical means for formalizing consistency rules and indicate how they are evaluated. For details see our companion paper [28].

3.1 Formalizing Consistency Rules

Consistency rules are statements about repository states,² which we call timestamps because they represent given points in time. Rule designers formalize rules in a variant of the two-sorted temporal first-order predicate logic with linear time and equality [2]. As usual in predicate logics, consistency rules use function symbols and predicate symbols, which we call both “symbols” throughout. The two-sorts approach to temporal logic introduces a new temporal sort Time. To each non-temporal symbol a timestamp is added – we call these symbols partially temporal. Fully temporal symbols have temporal arguments (and results) only. Quantifiers iterate over variables of the sort Time, too. For our purposes we generalize sorts towards types. Thus Time is a type, interpreted by repository states.

Fig. 3 shows part of our term and formula language – the rule designer’s toolset. Formulae mostly correspond to standard first-order formulae. A quantifier (\forall or \exists) introduces a bound variable x , restricted by a term e , which evaluates to the domain of x . We allow *rectified* formulae only, where each quantifier binds a different variable. Closed rectified formulae are called *consistency rules*. Typically, a rule carries additional metadata, e.g., whether it may be violated. Terms mostly correspond to [19]. We consider function symbols and record labels to be terms, too.

In the logic used here it is *undecidable* whether a formula is satisfiable. This is, however, no issue in our setting because rules are evaluated against concrete repositories. We,

²A state represents a repository snapshot at a given point in time. State transitions in the induced state automaton connect states in ascending order.

(1) Always links must be valid:
 “For all states t we have for all documents x at t that for all their referenced keys k there exists a key definition d (in one of the resolvers) for k and there exists a manual m with name and kind as defined by d .”

$$\phi_1 = \forall t \in \text{repStates} \bullet \forall x \in \text{repDs}(t) \bullet \forall k \in \text{refs}(x) \bullet \\ \exists d \in \text{concatMap}(\text{kDefs}, \text{repResDs}(t)) \bullet \\ \exists m \in \text{repManDs}(t) \bullet k = \text{key}(d) \wedge \\ \text{id}(m) = \text{kId}(d) \wedge \text{kind}(m) = \text{kKind}(d)$$

(2) Names and kinds of manuals are invariant over time:

“At all states t_1 we have for all manuals m_1 at t_1 that at all future states t_2 there exists a manual m_2 that has the same name and the same kind as m_1 .”

$$\phi_2 = \forall t_1 \in \text{repStates} \bullet \forall m_1 \in \text{repManDs}(t_1) \bullet \\ \forall t_2 \in \text{repStates} \bullet t_1 < t_2 \Rightarrow \\ \left(\exists m_2 \in \text{repManDs}(t_2) \bullet \right. \\ \left. \text{id}(m_1) = \text{id}(m_2) \wedge \text{kind}(m_1) = \text{kind}(m_2) \right)$$

Figure 4. Formal example rules

therefore, sacrifice decidability for expressivity. For some applications it might be interesting to know whether the rules are satisfiable or whether some rules are implied by others. Both questions reduce to the implication problem in predicate logic, which has been proven to be undecidable (see, e.g., [15]). Notice that in our setting “consistency checking” means to check how the repository conforms to the rules. This is in contrast to classic logic, where “consistency checking” means to determine whether a set of formulae has a model, i.e., all formulae can be fulfilled at once.

The language designer declares valid symbols for rule definition and defines the semantics of symbols in Haskell. Each symbol has a unique name. Due to their first temporal parameter the meaning of partially temporal symbols may change over time. For comparing timestamps we require a fully temporal predicate symbol \leq , interpreted by a total ordering relation, thus supporting linear time logic. Our static type system comprises record and variant types. Cardelli-style subtypes [1] prove practical for document management; we model document subsets from our example with the help of subtypes. We define a document type Doc to carry the name and the check-in time of a document; all other document types must be subtypes of Doc. They play an important rôle in incremental evaluation.

Example 2 A rule designer would formalize our consistency rules from Ex. 1 as shown in Fig. 4.

Rule ϕ_1 first quantifies over all states in the repository, provided by repStates . The term $\text{repDs}(t)$ returns the current documents for a state t . For each document x the variable k comprises the referenced keys, obtained by $\text{refs}(x)$.³ Key definitions in the resolvers are computed using the higher-order function concatMap . It applies kDefs to each key re-

³For convenience we allow to omit the temporal parameter for partially temporal symbols that are independent of time.

Type definitions		
Doc	= Doc	{id:String, time:Time}
		document
ManD < Doc	= Man	{kind:String}
		manual
ResD < Doc	= Res	{kDefs:[KDef]}
		key resolver
KDef	= KDef	{key, kId, kKind:String}
		key definition
Function symbol definitions		
repDs	: Time → [Doc]	get documents
repManDs	: Time → [ManD]	get manuals
repResDs	: Time → [ResD]	get key resolvers
refs	: Time × Doc → [String]	referenced keys
repStates	: [Time]	all repository states

Figure 5. Example language for rules in Fig. 4

solver, computed via $\text{repResDs}(t)$. When applied to a key resolver kDefs returns a list of key definitions. Finally, the resulting lists are concatenated. Thus d ranges over the key definitions from all key resolvers. The variable m ranges over all manuals at the state t , returned by $\text{repManDs}(t)$. We require that (1) the key k equals the key defined by the key definition d , (2) the name of the manual m equals the name d points to, and (3) the kind of m equals the kind d points to.

In rule ϕ_2 we twice quantify over time because we have to relate different versions of manuals: the old version at state t_1 , the new version at state t_2 .

The language designer defines the types and function symbols shown in Fig. 5 (definitions of standard types like lists $[]$ and Strings are omitted). We denote a subtype relation between record types by $<$. For example, the type for manuals ManD is a subtype of the general document type Doc . Thus ManD inherits all record labels from Doc . Labels induce new partially temporal function symbols, e.g., kDefs . We can use them as arguments of higher-order functions, e.g., in $\text{concatMap}(\text{kDefs}, \text{repResDs}(t))$. For brevity we omit the implementations of symbols used by our example. \square

3.2 Evaluating Consistency Rules

Our tolerant semantics pinpoints the trouble spots that make a repository inconsistent w.r.t. the formalized rules. The basic goal of our semantics is to provide authors the minimum information that precisely characterize when, where, and why a repository is inconsistent. Extending xlinkit^4 [18] we compute for each rule a *consistency report* containing a boolean result (representing boolean truth semantics) and a diagnosis set. Each diagnosis consists of a consistency flag, a variable assignment, fulfilled predicates, and failed predicates. A diagnosis (C, η, ps_t, ps_f) reads: “The processed formula is fulfilled (Consistent) for the variable assignment η due to true predicates ps_t and false predicates ps_f .” Similarly $(\text{IC}, \eta, ps_t, ps_f)$ indicates that the formula is violated

⁴The toolkit xlinkit statically checks *distributed* documents for consistency w.r.t. user defined rules, see Sect. 6.

state	repository changes	IC	CPU time
1	txt: 1n, key: 1n, man: 9n	0	5.23 sec.
2	txt: 1c, 4n	4	13.48 sec.
3	man: 2c	14	18.95 sec.
4	man: 2c	19	26.38 sec.
5	txt: 1c	21	33.40 sec.
6	txt: 1c	26	41.15 sec.
7	key: 1n	31	47.11 sec.
8	man: 1n	35	57.34 sec.
9	key: 1c	36	67.14 sec.

Figure 6. Brute force checking performance (tests were performed on a Dell X200 laptop; 800 MHz PIII CPU)

(InConsistent). The assignment η maps variables to concrete values, e.g., timestamps or documents. Due to temporal quantification it tells when and where a rule is violated. The predicate sets ps_t and ps_f give reasons for rule violation. Evaluating our example rules illustrates the above:

Example 3 Recall that in our introductory example (see Fig. 1) the second check-in causes two inconsistencies: (1) the key reference to kaA3 is inconsistent because the kind of the manual man1.xml is different from the kind of the key definition for kaA3 ; (2) the kind of man1.xml has changed. The consistency report for the rule ϕ_1 reflects the first inconsistency:

$$\left(\text{False}, \left\{ \left(\text{IC}, \left\{ \begin{array}{l} t \mapsto 2, k \mapsto \text{kaA3}, \\ x \mapsto \{\text{id} = \text{doc1.txt}, \text{time} = 1\} \end{array} \right\}, \right) \right\} \right)$$

The report’s assignment does not contain the variables d and m : the repository is inconsistent w.r.t. ϕ_1 for all possible assignments to d and m . The report also lacks the atomic formulae $k = \text{key}(d)$ and $\text{id}(m) = \text{kId}(d)$: The key resolver contains a definition for the key kaA3 , but this definition is inconsistent. A manual m with the correct name was found but it has the wrong kind. In other words, the first step of the link is consistent, the second step is inconsistent.

The second inconsistency is reflected by the report for ϕ_2 :

$$\left(\text{False}, \left\{ \left(\text{IC}, \left\{ \begin{array}{l} t_1 \mapsto 1, t_2 \mapsto 2, \\ m_1 \mapsto \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{id} = \text{man1.xml}, \text{time} = 1, \\ \text{kind} = \text{technical M.} \end{array} \right\} \end{array} \right\}, \right) \right\} \right)$$

The above report tells that for the manual man1.xml at state 1 no manual at state 2 could be found with the same kind. The report lacks $\text{id}(m_1) = \text{id}(m_2)$ because there exists a manual man1.xml at state 2: Its kind is wrong only. \square

3.3 Evaluation Time Complexity

We have integrated our consistency checker into the revision control system DARCS [26]. Evaluating our example

rules in a brute force manner results in an extremely poor performance. Fig. 6 shows the development of a “toy” repository, which we shall use throughout. The second column shows how many documents were added (n) or changed (c) by a check-in. We use `man` for manuals, `key` for key resolvers, and `txt` for text documents. Inconsistencies found when checking the rules ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 are summarized in the third column. The final column shows the CPU time needed for the consistency check. To a great extent CPU time depends on the repository state because a brute force checking has to evaluate *every* repository state.

The results in Fig. 6 are unacceptable but they are not surprising. Clearly, as in classic predicate logic, every quantifier domain contributes a polynomial factor; the nesting of quantifiers results in an exponential behavior. In order to make our approach viable it is absolutely necessary to develop methods that decrease evaluation time. In particular, evaluation time should not depend on the repository state.

4. Speeding up Consistency Checking

In this section we consider static and dynamic methods in order to decrease the computational complexity of evaluating first-order consistency rules. For simplicity we shall neglect the individual computational complexity of functions and predicates. We designed our methods to make minimal assumptions about the underlying DMS. We simply require (1) a repository to access past document versions, (2) a locking mechanism that prevents updates during a consistency check, and (3) that the DMS signals the documents modified by an update. Since we do not force a specific document model our techniques also apply to revision control systems, such as CVS or DARCS.

4.1 Static Analysis

Static analysis tries to localize and simplify consistency rules *before* they are evaluated against a repository. It is performed almost exclusively on a syntactical level. *Localizing* a rule means to associate it with the set of those documents that can possibly affect it. This reduces the number of rules to be re-evaluated at a repository check-in. A rule is *simplified* by minimizing its quantifier nesting and thus reducing the static evaluation time complexity. Our static methods are straightforward adaptations to database techniques [21, 12] that are already known. The following succinct introduction should, therefore, suffice.

When the DMS signals that the repository has changed, we want to re-evaluate only those consistency rules that might be affected by these updates. With each rule we associate a set of affected documents because we also target revision control systems, such as CVS, that lack a formal document model.⁵ Rule localization depends on appropriate metadata for functions and predicates. Static Haskell code analysis helps the

language designer to add these metadata. Then, a matching algorithm associates a consistency rule with a document set. For example, it associates the rule ϕ_1 with all plain text documents and all XML documents (`*.txt | *.xml`). That is because the function `repDs` accesses plain text documents and XML documents (`*.txt | *.xml`), `repManDs` accesses manuals only (`man*.xml`), and `repResDs` accesses key resolvers only (`key*.xml`). The rule ϕ_2 is associated with all manuals (`man*.xml`).

The computational cost to evaluate a consistency rule depends on its deepest quantifier nesting, which is minimal if the scope of each quantifier is minimal. Such formulae are called *miniscope* [9]. Consider the following variant of ϕ_1 :

$$\phi'_1 = \forall t \in \text{repStates} \bullet \forall x \in \text{repDs}(t) \bullet \forall k \in \text{refs}(x) \bullet \\ \exists d \in \text{concatMap}(\text{kDefs}, \text{repResDs}(t)) \bullet \\ k = \text{key}(d) \wedge \\ \left(\begin{array}{l} \exists m \in \text{repManDs}(t) \bullet \text{id}(m) = \text{kId}(d) \wedge \\ \text{kind}(m) = \text{kKind}(d) \end{array} \right)$$

Here, the existential quantifier over m was moved into the conjunction, which is sound because $k = \text{key}(d)$ does not contain the variable m . Since in ϕ'_1 the existential quantifier has a smaller scope, ϕ'_1 can be evaluated faster than ϕ_1 . For example, let each domain have a cardinality of n and each atomic formula evaluate in constant time c , then evaluating ϕ_1 costs $n^5 \cdot 3c$ whereas evaluating ϕ'_1 costs $n^4 \cdot c + n^5 \cdot 2c$ only.⁶ We adapt the techniques in [9] to convert our rules to miniscope. Miniscoping also removes implications, pushes negations into formulae, and “flattens” nested conjunctions and disjunctions. Our incremental evaluation algorithm benefits from these simplifications.

In rule ϕ_2 miniscoping replaces the implication by a disjunction. In addition, we push the universal quantifier over m_1 into the right hand side of this disjunction.

$$\phi'_2 = \forall t_1 \in \text{repStates} \bullet \forall t_2 \in \text{repStates} \bullet \\ \neg(t_1 < t_2) \vee \\ \left(\begin{array}{l} \forall m_1 \in \text{repManDs}(t_1) \bullet \exists m_2 \in \text{repManDs}(t_2) \bullet \\ \text{id}(m_1) = \text{id}(m_2) \wedge \text{kind}(m_1) = \text{kind}(m_2) \end{array} \right)$$

How does static analysis improve evaluation time? The second last column of Fig. 9 (see Sect. 4.4) shows benefits between 15% and 32%. Improvements achieved by miniscoping can be seen in states where both rules are re-evaluated. But still, the results are unsatisfactory: Rule evaluation time depends on the repository state. A major reason is that we access documents at *previous* repository states. Usually, the DMS rebuilds these documents step by step using state transition descriptions, e.g., diffs or patches. Next, we discuss dynamic methods, which attempt to avoid accessing past document versions. As we shall see, this improves performance significantly.

⁵In more sophisticated DMS we could also define document classes (so-called stereotypes) and associate these classes with consistency rules.

⁶Due to our simple example the speedup is not very impressive. For more complex rules we experienced greater speedups.

4.2 Incremental Evaluation

The major goals of incremental evaluation are: (1) access document versions only at the current state of the repository and (2) if possible access modified documents only. For static rules like ϕ'_1 , which do not depend on time, a very simple strategy would suffice: Just evaluate the rule for the new repository state and add the result to the accumulated previous reports. Alas this breaks down for temporal rules like ϕ'_2 , which relate different repository states.

Therefore, we have developed a general technique that applies to temporal rules, too. As usual, it is most challenging to balance the speedup gained against the space needed for storing auxiliary information. Our approach needs only little additional information (see Sect. 4.5). It exploits previous consistency reports in order to re-evaluate rules w.r.t. a part of the documents they affect. Our strategy is as follows:

1. Keep the old report from the previous evaluation.
2. If possible re-evaluate a quantifier inside a rule upon new or changed domain values only. For old domain values copy the relevant diagnoses from the old report.

A fundamental prerequisite to incremental evaluation is that the consistency report of a formula remains constant if its quantifier domains remain constant, i.e., the report depends on the free variables of a formula only. This requires that the result of a function or predicate depends on its parameters only – a feature called *referential transparency* in functional programming. Since language designers use Haskell to define symbol semantics, the above strategy is sound.⁷ A notable exception is the “unsafe” function `repStates`, which is not referentially transparent because it reads the number of already performed check-ins directly from the repository (see Sect. 4.5 for a discussion).

Since rule evaluation time depends mostly on the cardinality of quantifier domains we try to narrow them. We partition a quantifier domain into four sets: *new* contains new values, *chg* contains changed values, *del* contains deleted values, and *old* contains values that remained constant. We also extend variable assignments, which map variables to values, to also mark variables as new and old, respectively.

The central idea behind our incremental evaluation algorithm is to *re-evaluate a subformula only if contains a variable that is marked as new* in the current assignment or if it contains an unsafe function or predicate. If a subformula contains only old variables and only referentially transparent functions and predicates, we copy part of the old report and abort re-evaluation of this subformula.

Before detailing the formalism, we illustrate its effect on our running example:

Example 4 Consider at state 3 a check-in of a new manual `man2.xml`, which also references a key `kaA3`:

⁷In general, Haskell guarantees referential transparency. The use of Haskell is, however, not obligatory; any other referentially transparent programming language (excerpt) would suffice.

```
<man kind="field M.">
... <see>kaA3</see> ... </man>
```

We have to re-evaluate both rules. Fig. 7 shows how our incremental algorithm evaluates them. In the evaluation trees vertices represent conjunctions, disjunctions, or quantifier domains. Old values are printed in grey and new values in black. A path from the root to a leaf stands for an assignment.

When we evaluate the rule ϕ'_1 , the domain of the variable t is composed of the sets $new = \{3\}$, $chg = \emptyset$, $old = \{1, 2\}$, and $del = \emptyset$. Since t 's subformula contains only t freely and is referentially transparent we can abort re-evaluation for values in *old*. Instead, we copy relevant diagnoses from the old report, which results in a true report $(True, \emptyset)$ for $t \mapsto 1$ and the following report for $t \mapsto 2$ (we neglect variable markers in the assignments of diagnoses):

$$\left(\text{False}, \left(\left(\text{IC}, \{x \mapsto \{\text{id} = \text{doc1.txt}, \text{time} = 1\}, k \mapsto \text{kaA3}\}, \right), \right) \right)$$

The above report does not include the binding $t \mapsto 2$, which was removed while copying. When we finally evaluate t 's quantifier the binding for t is “pushed” in again.

For $t \mapsto 3$ we re-evaluate t 's subformula. Notice that the domain of k contains old values when it is evaluated for $x \mapsto \{\text{id} = \text{doc.txt}, \text{time} = 1\}$ because the bounding term $\text{refs}(x)$ contains the old variable x only. During copying we adapt the binding $t \mapsto (3, n)$ to the previous repository state $t \mapsto (2, n)$ because diagnoses in the old report cannot contain bindings to the new repository state. Other bindings to new values are neglected. In addition, we neglect bindings to existentially quantified variables because diagnoses contain bindings to universally quantified variables only. Thus we obtain:

$$\left(\text{False}, \left(\left(\text{IC}, \{x \mapsto \{\text{id} = \text{doc1.txt}, \text{time} = 1\}, k \mapsto \text{kaA3}\}, \right), \right) \right)$$

Finally, we push the binding $t \mapsto 2$ into the assignment of the copied report and the binding $t \mapsto 3$ into the assignments of the above report:

$$\left(\text{False}, \left(\left(\left(\text{IC}, \{t \mapsto 2, x \mapsto \{\text{id} = \text{doc1.txt}, \text{time} = 1\}, \}, \right), \right) \right) \right)$$

Evaluation of rule ϕ'_2 proceeds similarly to the evaluation of rule ϕ'_1 . The final report for rule ϕ'_2 at state 3 shows that state 1 is inconsistent with the states 2 and 3:

Evaluation tree for rule ϕ'_1

Evaluation tree for rule ϕ'_2

Figure 7. Incremental evaluation of rule ϕ'_1 and rule ϕ'_2

$\mathcal{R}_{(TL,I)} \llbracket p(e_0, e_1, \dots, e_n)^{xs} \rrbracket \eta \quad (p \text{ partially temporal})$ $= \text{copy}(p(e_0, e_1, \dots, e_n), \mathbb{R}, \eta) \text{ if } \text{notEval}(xs, \eta)$ $(\text{True}, \{(C, \emptyset, \{p(e_0, e_1, \dots, e_n)\}, \emptyset)\})$ $\text{if } (\mathcal{V}_{(TL,I)} \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket \eta, \dots, \mathcal{V}_{(TL,I)} \llbracket e_n \rrbracket \eta) \in p^{\dot{A}}$ $(\text{False}, \{(IC, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{p(e_0, e_1, \dots, e_n)\})\})$ otherwise <p>where $\dot{A} = I(\mathcal{V}_{TL} \llbracket e_0 \rrbracket \eta)$;</p> $\mathcal{R}_{(TL,I)} \llbracket p(e_1, \dots, e_n)^{xs} \rrbracket \eta \quad (p \text{ fully temporal})$ $= \text{copy}(p(e_1, \dots, e_n), \mathbb{R}, \eta) \text{ if } \text{notEval}(xs, \eta)$ $(\text{True}, \{(C, \emptyset, \{p(e_1, \dots, e_n)\}, \emptyset)\})$ $\text{if } (\mathcal{V}_{TL} \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket \eta, \dots, \mathcal{V}_{TL} \llbracket e_n \rrbracket \eta) \in p^{TL}$ $(\text{False}, \{(IC, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{p(e_1, \dots, e_n)\})\})$ otherwise $\mathcal{R}_A \llbracket \phi \wedge^{xs} \psi \rrbracket \eta = \text{copy}(\phi \wedge \psi, \mathbb{R}, \eta) \text{ if } \text{notEval}(xs, \eta)$ $r_\phi \otimes r_\psi \quad \text{if } \text{fst}(r_\phi) = \text{fst}(r_\psi) = \text{False}$ $r_\phi \quad \text{if } \text{fst}(r_\phi) = \text{False}$ $r_\psi \quad \text{if } \text{fst}(r_\psi) = \text{False}$ $(\text{True}, \emptyset) \quad \text{otherwise}$ <p>where $r_\phi = \mathcal{R}_A \llbracket \phi \rrbracket \eta$; $r_\psi = \mathcal{R}_A \llbracket \psi \rrbracket \eta$</p> $\mathcal{R}_A \llbracket \phi \vee^{xs} \psi \rrbracket \eta = \text{copy}(\phi \vee \psi, \mathbb{R}, \eta) \text{ if } \text{notEval}(xs, \eta)$ $r_\phi \oplus r_\psi \quad \text{if } \text{fst}(r_\phi) = \text{fst}(r_\psi) = \text{False}$ $(\text{True}, \emptyset) \quad \text{otherwise}$ <p>where $r_\phi = \mathcal{R}_A \llbracket \phi \rrbracket \eta$; $r_\psi = \mathcal{R}_A \llbracket \psi \rrbracket \eta$</p>	$\mathcal{R}_A \llbracket (\neg \phi)^{xs} \rrbracket \eta = \text{copy}(\neg \phi, \mathbb{R}, \eta) \text{ if } \text{notEval}(xs, \eta)$ $\overline{\text{flip}}(\mathcal{R}_A \llbracket \phi \rrbracket \eta) \quad \text{otherwise}$ $\mathcal{R}_A \llbracket \forall^{xs} x \in e \bullet \phi \rrbracket \eta = \text{copy}(\forall x \in e \bullet \phi, \mathbb{R}, \eta) \text{ if } \text{notEval}(xs, \eta)$ $\overline{\oplus}(F) \quad \text{if } F \neq \emptyset$ $(\text{True}, \emptyset) \quad \text{otherwise}$ <p>where $(\text{new}, \text{chg}, \text{old}, \text{del}) = \mathcal{V}_A \llbracket e \rrbracket \eta$</p> $rs = \{(v, \mathcal{R}_A \llbracket \phi \rrbracket \eta[x \mapsto (v, \circ)]) \mid v \in \text{old}\} \cup$ $\{(v, \mathcal{R}_A \llbracket \phi \rrbracket \eta[x \mapsto (v, n)]) \mid v \in \text{new} \cup \text{chg}\}$ $F = \{\text{push}(x \mapsto v, r) \mid (v, r) \in rs \text{ and } \text{fst}(r) = \text{False}\}$ $\mathcal{R}_A \llbracket \exists^{xs} x \in e \bullet \phi \rrbracket \eta = \text{copy}(\exists x \in e \bullet \phi, \mathbb{R}, \eta) \text{ if } \text{notEval}(xs, \eta)$ $(\text{False}, \{(IC, \emptyset, \{\text{null}(e)\}, \emptyset)\})$ $\text{if } T = F = \emptyset$ $\overline{\min}(F) \quad \text{if } T = \emptyset$ $(\text{True}, \emptyset) \quad \text{otherwise}$ <p>where $(\text{new}_0, \text{chg}, \text{old}_0, \text{del}) = \mathcal{V}_A \llbracket e \rrbracket \eta$</p> $\text{new} = \text{new}_0 \cup \text{old}_0 \cup \text{chg} \text{ if } \text{chg} \cup \text{del} \neq \emptyset$ $\text{new}_0 \quad \text{otherwise}$ $\text{old} = \emptyset \quad \text{if } \text{chg} \cup \text{del} \neq \emptyset$ $\text{old}_0 \quad \text{otherwise}$ $rs = \{\mathcal{R}_A \llbracket \phi \rrbracket \eta[x \mapsto (v, \circ)] \mid v \in \text{old}\} \cup$ $\{\mathcal{R}_A \llbracket \phi \rrbracket \eta[x \mapsto (v, n)] \mid v \in \text{new}\}$ $T = \{r \mid r \in rs \text{ and } \text{fst}(r) = \text{True}\}$ $F = \{r \mid r \in rs \text{ and } \text{fst}(r) = \text{False}\}$
---	---

Figure 8. Incremental evaluation algorithm (\mathbb{R} denotes the old report from the previous evaluation)

$$\left(\left(\text{False}, \left(\left(\left(IC, \left\{ \begin{array}{l} t_1 \mapsto 1, t_2 \mapsto 2, \\ m_1 \mapsto \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{id} = \text{man1.xml, time} = 2, \\ \text{kind} = \text{technical M.} \end{array} \right\} \end{array} \right\} \right), \left(\left\{ t_1 < t_2 \right\}, \left\{ \text{kind}(m_1) = \text{kind}(m_2) \right\} \right) \right) \right), \left(\left(IC, \left\{ \begin{array}{l} t_1 \mapsto 1, t_2 \mapsto 3, \\ m_1 \mapsto \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{id} = \text{man1.xml, time} = 2, \\ \text{kind} = \text{technical M.} \end{array} \right\} \end{array} \right\} \right), \left(\left\{ t_1 < t_2 \right\}, \left\{ \text{kind}(m_1) = \text{kind}(m_2) \right\} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

Due to our strategy, we copied diagnoses of the old report during evaluation of the *new* repository state ($t \mapsto 3$). Clearly, the simple strategy from the beginning of this section cannot achieve this. \square

4.3 An Incremental Evaluation Algorithm

In this section we formalize our new evaluation algorithm – an incremental variant a of brute force evaluation as presented in [28]. Recall that want to improve [28] as follows:

- We copy those parts from previous reports that have not changed.
- We partition quantifier domains into four sets: *new*, *chg*, *del*, and *old*. Variable assignments mark variables as

new and *old*, respectively. Our incremental algorithm deviates from brute force evaluation mostly in the treatment of quantified formulae.

- Due to miniscoping, only atomic formulae can appear negated. In particular, existential quantifiers cannot appear “disguised” as universal quantifiers and vice versa. This simplifies our evaluation algorithm considerably.

Fig. 8 shows the denotational semantics of our incremental report generation algorithm. The function $\mathcal{R}_A \llbracket \phi \rrbracket \eta$ traverses the structure of a formula ϕ (like in classic boolean evaluation of predicate logic formulae). A denotes a first-order temporal structure,⁸ η stands for the current variable assignment. For readability we introduce a global variable \mathbb{R} , which represents the old report. Superscripts denote the free variables of a formula; ϕ^{xs} means that the variables from the set xs are free in ϕ . For brevity we omit a formal definition of auxiliary functions.

⁸As usual, we interpret temporal formulae in first-order temporal structures $A = (TL, I)$, which consist of a timeline TL (interpreting temporal types and fully temporal symbols) and a function I (associating a time w with a non-temporal structure $\dot{A} = I(w)$, which interprets non-temporal types and partially temporal symbols). The domain of the type `Time` is the set of natural numbers \mathbb{N} , representing repository states.

For every formula $\text{notEval}(xs, \eta)$ determines whether all free variables xs are marked as old in the current assignment η and it contains referentially transparent functions and predicates only. In this case, we copy the relevant diagnoses from the old report \mathbb{R} , where (1) bindings to the current repository state are replaced with bindings to the previous repository state and (2) bindings of existentially quantified variables and bindings to new values are neglected. A diagnosis in the old report may contain an assignment that is more detailed than η . Therefore, we copy all diagnoses containing assignments that are subsumed by η .⁹ In order to identify the relevant diagnoses copy needs as additional argument the formula ϕ currently processed. We copy only those diagnoses that contain predicates occurring in ϕ . This is necessary because for conjunctions and disjunctions reports are combined.

For an atomic formula we create a new report with only one diagnosis. Depending on its truth value the formula itself is pushed into one of the predicate sets (ps_t and ps_f , respectively). We store the complete atomic formula in order to identify predicate symbols that occur more than once in a consistency rule. The function $\mathcal{V}_A[[e]]\eta$ calculates the value of a term e w.r.t. a temporal structure A and an assignment η as in classic predicate logic.

If a conjunction $\phi \wedge \psi$ is violated we retain the reports of subformulae that are “responsible” for this inconsistency. If both ϕ and ψ are violated we compute the cartesian product of their reports by the auxiliary function \otimes . Otherwise, we retain the report of the false subformula, which causes the violation of the conjunction. For disjunctions we use a similar approach but join reports via \oplus .

We have reached the heart of our algorithm: the treatment of quantifiers.

For a universally quantified formula $\forall x \in e \bullet \phi$ we first compute the domain, resulting in the four sets *new*, *chg*, *old*, and *del*. They are computed by the function $\mathcal{D}_A[[e]]\eta$, which we discuss in Sect. 4.5. We mark the values in *new* \cup *chg* as new (n) and the values in *old* as old (o). Then the subformula ϕ is evaluated for possible assignment extensions to these values ($\eta[x \mapsto (v, n)]$ and $\eta[x \mapsto (v, o)]$, respectively). If ϕ is violated for an assignment extension we push the current variable binding $x \mapsto v$ into the variable assignment of each diagnosis in ϕ 's report. Finally, $\overline{\oplus}$ joins the resulting reports in F .

Evaluation of an existentially quantified formula is slightly more complicated. Here the above procedure is sound only if no values were changed or deleted in the domain, i.e., $chg \cup del = \emptyset$. Naturally, an existentially quantified formula can become false if values in its domain are deleted. Adding new values to the domain cannot falsify an existentially quantified formula. Consequently, if $chg \cup del$ contains values we must mark *every* domain value as new in the assignment extensions. So the worst cases for incremental evaluation are changed or deleted values in domains of existential quanti-

state	repository changes	rules	CPU time (4.1)	CPU time (4.1 & 4.3)
1	txt: 1n, key: 1n, man: 9n	ϕ_1, ϕ_2	4.44 sec.	4.47 sec.
2	txt: 1c, 4n	ϕ_1	9.55 sec.	2.33 sec.
3	man: 2c	ϕ_1, ϕ_2	15.25 sec.	6.45 sec.
4	man: 2c	ϕ_1, ϕ_2	20.40 sec.	6.58 sec.
5	txt: 1c	ϕ_1	23.46 sec.	2.68 sec.
6	txt: 1c	ϕ_1	27.98 sec.	2.53 sec.
7	key: 1n	ϕ_1	32.50 sec.	3.09 sec.
8	man: 1n	ϕ_1, ϕ_2	44.66 sec.	4.01 sec.
9	key: 1c	ϕ_1	45.34 sec.	3.61 sec.

Figure 9. Improvements by static analysis (4.1) and incremental evaluation (4.3)

fiers. If an existentially quantified formula is violated we minimize the report set F because we do not know which values are responsible for this inconsistency. Our solution is to blame those values that caused the “least violations;” i.e., their diagnoses contain the least amount of predicates. In addition, we handle the special case when the domain of an existentially quantified formula is empty. Then we generate a new diagnosis, which tells that the empty domain e causes an inconsistency ($\text{null}(e)$ means that e is empty).

We could weaken the above restrictions by adding explicit information to the reports stating which values in the domain of an existential quantifier made a rule consistent or inconsistent. We would really like to do so but we found that reports become extremely large if we store these additional values. Therefore, our tradeoff is to avoid storing these additional information even though evaluation of existential quantifiers can be slower than evaluation of universal quantifiers. Universal quantifiers do not suffer from changed or deleted domain values because our reports already store the values that make a rule inconsistent – they pinpoint inconsistencies.

4.4 Achievements by Incremental Evaluation

Let us return to our example repository. What does incremental evaluation buy? The last column in Fig. 9 shows the performance of our consistency checker using both static analysis and incremental evaluation. Now, evaluation time depends on the changed content rather than on the repository state. Notice that the primitive strategy described at the beginning of Sect. 4.2 cannot achieve the following: Except for the states 3 and 4, every evaluation is faster than the initial evaluation *although* the repository grows. Further experiments [30] also show that our consistency checker performs at reasonable speed.

4.5 Technical Notes

In this section, we discuss some of the rather technical details we came across while implementing our incremental evaluation algorithm.

⁹An assignment η_1 is subsumed an assignment η_2 if each variable binding in η_2 also occurs in η_1 , where we neglect variable markers.

We access the repository through some functions to get the timestamps of already performed check-ins (`repStates`), get documents at a given check-in time, and parse documents (see Sect. 5.1). The repository guarantees that, except for `repStates`, interface functions are referentially transparent although they involve IO. The interface function `repStates` cannot be referentially transparent because it reads the timestamps of already performed check-ins directly from the repository, and thus its result changes between (but not during) consistency checks. Straightforward source code analysis determines whether a function or predicate defined by the language designer is referentially transparent, i.e., it does not call `repStates` directly or indirectly.

A simple approach to incremental evaluation would require to store *every* quantifier domain from the previous evaluation. This is, however, not feasible because quantifier domains can become unexpectedly large since we do not control their vocabulary. For example, a quantifier might iterate over the complete document content. Instead of storing domains, we *memoize* certain functions that occur in quantifier bounding terms [3]. This reduces the space needed for storing intermediate data and maximizes the benefits for incremental evaluation. We distinguish functions by their result type. Storing timestamps is cheap. We also consider documents by exploiting a natural property of a DMS: A document can be identified by its name and check-in time. Since we only need to know whether a document has been modified by a check-in we store the “Doc-part” of each function the result type of which is a subtype of `[Doc]`. Thus we neglect additional record labels, such as `kind` in the record type `ManD`. In summary, we memoize each function that occurs in a quantifier bounding term and has either `[Time]` or a subtype of `[Doc]` as result type. In our example these are: `repStates`, `repDs`, `repResDs`, and `repManDs`.

The function \mathcal{D} computes the domain of a quantifier. If \mathcal{D} encounters an applied function symbol returning a result of either type `[Time]` or a subtype of `[Doc]` it calculates the four lists *new*, *chg*, *old*, and *del* from the current result and the stored result from the previous evaluation. These lists are propagated up the term structure. Therefore, some restrictions apply to quantifier bounding terms. We only permit functions that treat each list member separately, e.g., `concatMap`. We apply \mathcal{D} also to bounding terms that lack memoized functions, e.g., `refs(x)` in ϕ_1 . If a free variable of a bounding term is marked as *new* in the current assignment or the term is unsafe the lists *old*, *chg*, and *del* are empty and *new* contains the complete domain. Otherwise, if all free variables of a bounding term are marked as *old* in the current assignment and the term is referentially transparent, \mathcal{D} returns all domain values in *old* leaving *new*, *chg*, and *del* empty. This is sound because due to referential transparency the domain cannot have changed.

5. Implementing Consistency Rules

This section gives an overview of our implementation and presents some lessons learned from our experiments.

5.1 Prototype Implementation

How do we perform a consistency check in practice? Currently, we interface the revision control system DARCS [26]. Now consider the situation where an author checks in a document. DARCS first performs some tests to ensure that the changes submitted may be applied to the repository. If this test succeeds, DARCS calls our consistency checker through a system call (we use system calls because of their simplicity). During the execution of our consistency checker the repository is locked, i.e., any check-ins are prohibited. If all strict rules are satisfied, our consistency checker terminates successfully and DARCS acknowledges the check-in. Otherwise, the check-in is rejected.

Our consistency checker reads the rules to check from the project description supplied by the project manager. The next step is to type-check the rules against the functions and predicates they use. Typically, the languages used do not change between consistency checks and we dynamically link auxiliary Haskell modules to the running consistency checker (the modules have been compiled during a previous consistency check). These modules contain implementations of functions, predicates, and types. Haskell lacks subtyping. We, therefore, resolve subtype relationships through (1) coercion functions, which coerce a subtype to a supertype, and (2) marshalling functions, which convert a Haskell value into a value as required by our consistency checker. Now, we can call the functions and predicates defined by the language designer in order to check the repository for consistency. Consistency checking uses the algorithm already explained in Sect. 4.3. If, however, a language used has changed since the previous consistency check, we re-compile it with the help of the Haskell compiler GHC [34]. GHC also type-checks the implementations of functions and predicates. All this is performed in the background.

As already mentioned we make only few assumptions about the underlying DMS or revision control system. We have developed a simple repository interface, which must be instantiated for a specific DMS. The interface consists of five Haskell functions (`Rep` is a Haskell type, which represents the repository):

- `repStates :: Rep → [Time]` returns all states of a given repository.
- `repDocs :: Rep → Time → String → [Doc]` returns the documents in the repository that are current at a given time and match a regular expression. For example, `repDocs repo 2 "*" ".xml"` returns all XML documents current at state 2.
- `repDirs :: Rep → Time → String → [Dir]` behaves similarly to `repDocs` but returns directories instead.

- `parseDoc :: Rep → Doc → (String → a) → Maybe a` accesses a given document in the repository. The third parameter is a function that parses the document content and converts it into an appropriate Haskell data structure. For XML documents such parser functions can be generated [35].
- `repChanges :: Time → Rep → [String]` returns a list of document names and directory names that have been modified since the previous evaluation, determined by the first parameter.

Except for `repChanges` the interface functions above can be used by the language designer. Our tools generate the repository argument and provide it as a top-level function. The interface function `repChanges` is essential for filtering consistency rules.

5.2 Lessons Learned

In order to test the feasibility and the practical relevance of our approach, we currently run a project together with `sd&m`¹⁰ – a well established software company in Munich, Germany. We have formalized consistency rules for `sd&m`'s analysis modules [33, 30] – a *document*-based approach to software specification. Applied to an example specification, our consistency checker precisely identifies inconsistencies such that developers can concentrate on their real work, namely that the specification reflects the requirements of the specified system. Due to incremental consistency checking, our prototype performs at reasonable speed.

Prior to their formalization, consistency requirements were described in natural language only and were distributed over all analysis modules. Requirements were imprecise, thus leading to misinterpretations and contradictions. Worse, software engineers had to spend a lot of time just to ensure formal consistency between the documents of a specification.

Formalizing consistency requirements as rules and collecting them in a rule system has resulted in a more precise understanding of what consistency means. We have also learned to understand the consistency rules themselves better. Some rules have been dropped because they have failed to reflect what was really meant from a software engineering point of view. Subtypes have played an important rôle: they have significantly decreased the number of types and functions. This has simplified the task of formalization. We have also learned to appreciate our type checker, which has pinpointed a lot of formalization errors especially for uses of polymorphic higher-order functions.

Since we do not assume a specific document model, our approach to incrementality is quite coarse-grained. Therefore, our incremental algorithm performs better for small documents than for large documents. Our experiments have also shown that our tolerant approach to consistency is the only way to handle a repository in progress. In fact, most of our

rules are weak. Making these rules strict, i.e., prohibiting their violation, almost immediately produces deadlocks: software developers cannot check in their work anymore.

There are also some issues. We have spent much time in formalizing the rules and in defining appropriate types, functions, and predicates. Still, formalization is a complex task. We are, however, convinced that the benefits of our approach outweigh the costs, which occur only once.

6. Related Work

Since managing consistency is a fundamental problem a huge body of related work exists; see, e.g., [18, 28]. Here, we focus on incremental consistency checking and only discuss some closely related work in this area. In contrast to our approach, most of the other incremental approaches *enforce* consistency and thus benefit from total satisfaction of consistency rules prior to consistency checking.

Incremental programming languages [14, 3] provide a uniform approach to incremental computation. They attempt to minimize redundant computation provided that a program is executed repeatedly on slightly different inputs. In order to produce the current results of a program run, incremental computation uses previous results, differences between previous inputs and current inputs, and auxiliary information. Our treatment of quantifier domains follows this approach. We can regard a quantified formula as a “function” having the quantifier domain as input, which is reduced during incremental evaluation.

Instead of miniscoping [9], we could also employ quantifier elimination techniques, known from theorem provers [6], in order to reduce the static complexity of our consistency rules. This would, however, eliminate quantified variables, which provide a precise characterization of inconsistencies.

From its origin, the database community has been striving for efficient algorithms that check integrity constraints [25, 21, 31, 12], maintain views [11, 17], and optimize queries [5]. Usually, these approaches employ the following techniques: *Compile-time* analysis simplifies integrity constraints and identifies update types that might violate constraints. *Run-time* approaches use previous results to avoid re-computation. In the context of first-order logic they reduce quantifier domains. In general, we follow the approach of the database community but do not have a formal database schema, formalized updates, and consistency prior to updates. This makes our approach more complicated. We cannot benefit from constraint subsumption because this is undecidable in our rule language; miniscoping performs only some very simple subsumption analysis. Localizing rules roughly corresponds to using update information in [12]. Our approach cannot show the high performance found in databases because we do not make any assumptions to the document model of the underlying DMS. In document management, however, our approach suffices because typically DMS do not have to carry the high load of databases. In (temporal) databases the problem of efficiently storing and manag-

¹⁰see www.sdm.de

ing historical database states arises. In our setting, historical repository states are already managed by the DMS.

Recently, incremental evaluation techniques have been used by the XML community to maintain consistency w.r.t. user defined rules [13]. The consistency checking toolkit xlinkit [22] uses static analysis to filter consistency rules relevant to document changes and a treediff algorithm to determine document parts that have to be re-checked. Its tolerant view of consistency distinguishes xlinkit from other approaches and makes it closer to our approach. By allowing distribution and avoiding a history-aware repository, xlinkit cannot implement temporal consistency rules and lacks some of the incremental techniques we benefit from.

7. Conclusion and Outlook

This paper is concerned with the efficient evaluation of first-order temporal consistency rules by employing incremental techniques. Exploiting domain knowledge supplied by the language designer, we statically analyze consistency rules: (1) we associate with each rule a document set the rule depends on; (2) we miniscope rules in order to reduce their static evaluation time complexity. At run-time we re-evaluate a rule only on modified documents if possible. Haskell's referential transparency is a fundamental prerequisite for the soundness of our techniques. Our performance measurements prove that static analysis combined with incremental evaluation results in a significant speedup compared to brute force evaluation. We conjecture that our incremental evaluation algorithm could be of value in other research areas as well.

In the future, we will focus on fine tuning our incremental approach based on further experiments. Sophisticated caching techniques, which consider function and predicate properties (such as transitivity), become important when evaluating complex functions and predicates. Function and predicate properties also may help to take advantage of rewriting techniques in the GHC [24]. In addition, we develop strategies to suggest repairs that can resolve inconsistencies [29].

Extending previous work [28], the contributions of this paper provide the key to make our approach to consistency management viable.¹¹

8. References

- [1] M. Abadi and L. Cardelli. *A Theory of Objects*. Springer-Verlag, 1996.
- [2] S. Abiteboul, L. Herr, and J. van den Bussche. Temporal versus first-order logic to query temporal databases. In *ACM Symp. on Principles of Database Systems*, pages 49–57, Montreal, Canada, 1996. ACM Press.
- [3] U. A. A. Acar, G. E. Blleloch, and R. Harper. Selective memoization. In *Proc. of the 30th ACM SIGPLAN-SIGACT Symp. on Principles of Programming Languages*, pages 14–25, New Orleans, LA, 2003. ACM Press.
- [4] T. E. Ahlswede and R. Y. Lee. Cognitive issues in software requirements analysis. In *Proc. of the 4th Int. Conf. on Software Engineering, Artificial Intelligence, Networking, and Parallel/Distributed Computing (SNPD'03)*, pages 113–119, Lübeck, Germany, 2003. ACIS.
- [5] L. Baekgaard and L. Mark. Incremental computation of nested relational query expressions. *ACM Trans. on Database Systems (TODS)*, 20(2):111–148, 1995.
- [6] S. Basu. New results on quantifier elimination over real closed fields and applications to constraint databases. *J. ACM*, 46(4):537–555, 1999.
- [7] P. Cederqvist et al. Version management with CVS, 2002. see www.cvshome.org/docs/manual/.
- [8] Chakravarty, M. (ed). The Haskell foreign function interface 1.0, addendum to the Haskell 98 report, 2003. see www.cse.unsw.edu.au/~chak/haskell/ffi/.
- [9] D. de Champeaux. Subproblem finder and instance checker, two cooperating modules for theorem provers. *J. ACM*, 33(4):633–657, 1986.
- [10] A. Finkelstein. A foolish consistency: Technical challenges in consistency management. In *Proc. of the 11th Int. Conf. on Database and Expert Systems Applications (DEXA)*, pages 1–5, London, U.K., 2000. Springer-Verlag.
- [11] A. Gupta, I. Mumick, and V. Subrahmanian. Maintaining views incrementally. In *Proc. of the 1993 ACM SIGMOD Int. Conf. on Management of Data*, pages 157–166, Washington, DC, 1993. ACM Press.
- [12] A. Gupta, Y. Sagiv, J. Ullman, and J. Widom. Constraint checking with partial information. In *Proc. of the 13th ACM SIGACT-SIGMOD-SIGART Symp. on Principles of Database Systems*, pages 45–55, Minneapolis, MS, 1994. ACM Press.
- [13] B. Kane, H. Su, and E. Rundensteiner. Consistently updating XML documents using incremental constraint check queries. In *Proc. of the 4th Int. Workshop on Web Information and Data Management*, pages 1–8, McLean, VA, 2002. ACM Press.
- [14] Y. A. Liu. Efficiency by incrementalization: An introduction. *Higher Order Symbol. Comput.*, 13(4):289–313, 2000.
- [15] E. Mendelson. *Introduction to Mathematical Logic*. Wadsworth & Brooks/Cole Advanced Books & Software, 3rd edition, 1987.
- [16] Minister of Defence. *ZDv 90/1 – Dienstvorschriften der Bundeswehr*. Department of Defence, 1983. (English: Service Manual Rules for the Federal Armed Forces).
- [17] G. Moro and C. Sartori. Incremental maintenance of multi-source views. In *Proc. of the 12th Australasian Database Conference*, pages 13–20, Australia, 2001. IEEE.
- [18] C. Nentwich, L. Capra, W. Emmerich, and A. Finkelstein. xlinkit: a consistency checking and smart link generation service. *ACM Trans. Inter. Tech.*, 2(2):151–185, 2002.
- [19] J. Nordlander. Polymorphic subtyping in O'Haskell. *Science of Computer Programming*, 43(2-3):93–127, 2002.
- [20] B. Nuseibeh, S. Easterbrook, and A. Russo. Leveraging inconsistency in software development. *IEEE Computer*, 33(4):24–29, 2000.
- [21] M. A. Pacheco e Silva. Dynamic integrity constraints definition and enforcement in databases: a classification framework. In *Proc. of the IFIP TC-11 Working Group 11.5 First Working Conf. on Integrity and Internal Control in Information Systems*, pages 65–87, Zürich, Switzerland, 1997.

¹¹For further information see our www site www2-data.informatik.unibw-muenchen.de/cde.html.

- [22] C. Perez-Arroyo, C. Nentwich, W. Emmerich, and A. Finkelstein. Scaling consistency checking. submitted, 2003. see www.cs.ucl.ac.uk/staff/nentwich/publications/scalingchecking.html.
- [23] S. Peyton Jones. *Haskell 98 Language and Libraries: The Revised Report*. Cambridge University Press, 2003.
- [24] S. Peyton Jones, A. Tolmach, and T. Hoare. Playing by the rules: Rewriting as a practical optimisation technique in GHC. In *Proc. of the 2001 ACM SIGPLAN Haskell Workshop (HW '2001)*, pages 203–233, Firenze, Italy, 2001. ACM Press.
- [25] D. Plexousakis. *On the Efficient Maintenance of Temporal Integrity in Knowledge Bases*. PhD thesis, University of Toronto, 1996.
- [26] D. Roundy. Darcs: David's advanced revision control system, 2004. see www.abridgegame.org/darcs/.
- [27] G. Salton. Automatic indexing and abstracting. In *Document retrieval systems*, pages 42–80. Taylor Graham Publishing, 1988.
- [28] J. Scheffczyk, U. M. Borghoff, P. Rödig, and L. Schmitz. Consistent document engineering. In *Proc. of the 2003 ACM Symp. on Document Engineering*, pages 140–149, Grenoble, France, 2003. ACM Press.
- [29] J. Scheffczyk, U. M. Borghoff, P. Rödig, and L. Schmitz. S-DAGs: Towards efficient document repair generation. In *Proc. of the 2nd Intl. Conf. on Computing, Communications and Control Technologies (CCCT'04)*, Austin, TX, to appear 2004.
- [30] J. Scheffczyk, C. Stutz, U. M. Borghoff, and J. Siedersleben. Formale Konsistenzsicherung in informellen Software-Spezifikationen. *Informatik Forschung und Entwicklung*, 19(1):17–29, 2004. (English: Ensuring Formal Consistency of Informal Software Specifications).
- [31] R. Seljée and H. de Swart. Three types of redundancy in integrity checking; an optimal solution. In *Proc. of Data and Knowledge Engineering*, pages 135–151, Sidney, Australia, 1999.
- [32] K. Shafer, S. Weibel, E. Jul, and J. Fausey. Introduction to persistent uniform resource locators, 1996. see url.oclc.org/OCLC/PURL/INET96.
- [33] C. Stutz, J. Siedersleben, D. Kretschmer, and W. Krug. Analysis beyond UML. In *Proc. of RE'02: IEEE Joint Int. Requirements Engineering Conf. 2002*, pages 215–222, Essen, Germany, 2002. IEEE.
- [34] The GHC Team. GHC – The Glasgow Haskell Compiler. see www.haskell.org/ghc, 2004.
- [35] M. Wallace and C. Runciman. Haskell and XML: Generic combinators or type-based translation? In *Proc. of the 4th ACM SIGPLAN Int. Conf. on Functional Programming (ICFP'99)*, volume 34–9, pages 148–159, Paris, France, 1999. ACM Press.

Jan Scheffczyk received his Diploma degree in Computer Science at the Universität der Bundeswehr München, Munich, Germany (UniBwM) in 2001. Since 2002 he is research assistant at the Institute for Software Technology of the UniBwM. His research interests include consistency maintenance in document engineering, long-term preservation of digital data, and software engineering.

Uwe Borghoff holds Diploma and Doctoral degrees in Computer Science from the TU Munich, Germany. In 1993, he was awarded the postdoctoral university lecturing qualification (Habilitation) in Computer Science. He worked at the TU Munich for seven years as research scientist before joining the Xerox Research Centre Europe (formerly Rank Xerox Research Centre) at the Grenoble Laboratory, France, in 1994. In 1998, he joined the Faculty of the UniBwM, where he is a full professor of Computer Science at the Institute for Software Technology. Since 2002, he is the Dean of the Faculty of Computer Science.

ble Laboratory, France, in 1994. In 1998, he joined the Faculty of the UniBwM, where he is a full professor of Computer Science at the Institute for Software Technology. Since 2002, he is the Dean of the Faculty of Computer Science.

Peter Rödig received his Engineering Diploma degree at the TU Munich in 1984. Since 1984 he is research assistant at the UniBwM. He started at the Lab of Computer Science in Engineering, where he designed and implemented large-scale decision support and document management systems. Now he develops methods for long-term preservation of digital data at the Institute for Software Technology.

Further research interests include document engineering and database technology.

Lothar Schmitz graduated from TU Munich in 1975. He now is a university lecturer at UniBwM, where he obtained his Ph.D. in 1982. In the academic year 1993/4 he temporarily held the position of a professor at LMU Munich and again in 1997 at TU Dresden, where he completed his habilitation in 2001. His research interests include formal program development methods, visual compiler

compilers, software engineering, and long-term preservation of digital data.